

Analyzing ZED-2 Flooding Experiments for CANDU Coolant Void Reactivity Validation

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ABSTRACT

Two ZED-2 flooding experiments, one utilizing natural uranium (NU) and the other mixed-oxide (MOX) fuel, were used to validate the predictions of coolant void reactivity (CVR) for an equilibrium CANDU reactor lattice. The TSUNAMI validation framework was used to calculate the similarity of the experiments to the application and to determine nuclear data adjustments and corresponding computational biases. Both experiments had positive flooding biases resulting in a negative CVR bias for the CANDU application. The inclusion of the MOX data provided only a slight additional reduction in CVR uncertainty compared to the NU data alone. The CVR bias determined using both the NU and MOX data is 0.33 mk.

Keywords: Benchmark experiments, validation, CANDU, coolant void reactivity, ZED-2

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Motivation

Coolant void reactivity (CVR) is well known to be positive in CANDU reactors, and its value impacts the prediction of reactor behaviour during events such as loss-of-coolant accidents (LOCAs). Flooding experiments, generally utilizing fresh CANDU fuel, have been used to validate CVR calculations. However, CVR is known to vary with burnup [1], in part due to the production of plutonium, which suggests that flooding experiments utilizing mixed oxide (MOX) fuel could further improve CVR predictions. This work investigates the use of flooding experimental data from the Zero Energy Deuterium 2 (ZED-2) reactor for validating CVR calculations, and evaluates the benefit of incorporating additional MOX data to improve validation with burnup.

1.2. Code Validation

When utilizing high fidelity Monte Carlo neutron transport codes, the underlying nuclear data are generally the most significant source of response uncertainty. Consequently, the validation approach considered in this work, consistent with the TSUNAMI methodology within the SCALE code system [2], utilizes experimental data to reduce nuclear data uncertainties and determine associated computational biases.

Flooding experiments in the ZED-2 reactor determine a set of critical configurations; each with a different number of flooded channels and corresponding critical D₂O height. These configurations can be modelled by a neutron transport code, and any deviation in the predicted k_{eff} response from unity indicates a computational bias. The difference between the computational k_{eff} bias of the air-cooled and flooded configurations indicates a 'flooding bias', which, through the adjustment of nuclear data,

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can be used to determine the CVR bias of the application. The flooding bias ($\beta_{flooding}$) is the reactivity difference between the bias of the air-cooled (β_{air}) and flooded ($\beta_{flooded}$) configurations.

$$\beta_{flooding} = \beta_{flooded} - \beta_{air} = \left(\frac{1}{k_{flooded}^m} - \frac{1}{k_{flooded}^c} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{k_{air}^m} - \frac{1}{k_{air}^c} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where the superscripts c and m denote the calculated and measured k_{eff} values. The measured k_{eff} values are generally equal to 1, as each corresponds to a critical configuration.

Many nuclear data adjustment validation approaches exist, but the most straight forward involves the use of the General Linear Least Squares (GLLS) methodology and first-order nuclear data sensitivity coefficients. Sensitivity coefficients are the relative partial derivative of k_{eff} to a specific cross section. The difference in the k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients between nominal and voided (or an air-cooled and flooded) configurations give the CVR (or flooding) sensitivity coefficients, denoted by the reactivity symbol ρ .

$$S_{k,\alpha_{n,x,g}} = \frac{\alpha_{n,x,g}}{k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial \alpha_{n,x,g}} \quad S_{\rho,\alpha} = \frac{\frac{1}{k_2} S_{k2,\alpha} - \frac{1}{k_1} S_{k1,\alpha}}{|\rho_{1 \rightarrow 2}|} \quad (2)$$

Where $\alpha_{n,x,g}$ represents a cross section associated with a specific interaction (x) between an incident neutron and a target nuclide (n) within a defined neutron energy range (g) and the subscripts 1 and 2 denote the nominal and voided configurations. In this work, TSUNAMI-2D, within the SCALE 6.3 code suite, was used to produce the sensitivity coefficients, while MCNP 6.2 was used to calculate the experimental computational biases [2, 3].

The GLLS methodology determines the nuclear data adjustments associated with a set of experiments by minimizing the χ^2 discrepancy:

$$\chi^2 = [\Delta\alpha]^T \mathbf{C}_{\alpha\alpha}^{-1} [\Delta\alpha] + [\Delta\mathbf{m}]^T \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{m}\mathbf{m}}^{-1} [\Delta\mathbf{m}] \quad (3)$$

Where $\Delta\alpha$ represents adjustments to the nuclear data cross sections, $\mathbf{C}_{\alpha\alpha}$ denotes the nuclear data covariance matrix, $\Delta\mathbf{m}$ signifies the discrepancy between modelled and measured experimental results, and $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{m}\mathbf{m}}$ denotes the experimental covariance matrix.

The CVR bias is then given by:

$$\text{CVR}_{bias} = \text{CVR}_{calculated} - \text{CVR}_{adjusted} \quad (4)$$

Where $\text{CVR}_{adjusted}$ is the CVR value that would be calculated if the adjusted nuclear data cross sections were used. This is consistent with the TSURFER methodology described in the SCALE code system documentation [2]. In this work the ENDF B-VII.1 nuclear data library, and its associated covariances, were utilized [4]. The resulting biases and uncertainties are only relevant to this nuclear data library.

1.3. Application of Interest

The application of interest in this work is a 2x2 CANDU lattice in which the D₂O coolant density is reduced from 0.81 to 0.01 g/cm³. The miniature lattice consists of two fresh 37-element bundles, and two bundles with compositions representative of 7.00 MWd/kgHM of burnup. This application is intended to represent an equilibrium CANDU lattice, in which burnup varies between fuel channels due to on-line bi-directional fuelling. This application was modelled in TSUNAMI-2D, which uses the transport solver NEWT, to determine the CVR response and the corresponding nuclear data sensitivity coefficients [2]. The 2x2 lattice configuration, and the first group flux, are provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Geometry (left) and first-group (fast, 1 of 56 energy groups) flux (right) of the CANDU 2x2 lattice application as modelled in TSUNAMI-2D.

2. ZED-2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1. Configurations

Two ZED-2 flooding experimental configurations were considered in this work. One, *ZED2-HWR-EXP-001*, which utilizes natural uranium fuel (NU), is described within the International Handbook of Evaluated Reactor Physics Benchmark Experiments (IRPhE) [5, 6]. The second configuration features 36-element MOX fuel [7] surrounded by CANFLEX driver fuel [8], where only the MOX channels are flooded during the experiment. The top/lattice view of the two experimental configurations, NU and MOX fueled, are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. ZED-2 flooding experiment configurations: NU experiment (left) and MOX experiment (right) [6].

A summary of the application and experimental characteristics is provided in Table I. Notably, the experimental systems are at much lower temperatures than the application and utilize aluminum pressure and calandria tubes, rather than Zircaloy tubes. The two experiments considered also have different lattice structures, with the NU experiment arranged in a hexagonal lattice and the MOX experiment in a

square lattice.

Table I. Application and experimental details.

	CANDU Application	ZED-2 NU [6]	ZED-2 MOX
Fuel	37-Element NU Bundles	28-Element NU Bundles	CANFLEX (LEU) and 36-Element MOX Bundles
Fuel Temperature (K)	960	295	295
Coolant	D ₂ O	D ₂ O	D ₂ O
Coolant Temperature	561	295	295
Moderator Type	D ₂ O	D ₂ O	D ₂ O
Moderator Temperature	342	295	295
Pressure Tube	Zircaloy	Aluminum	Aluminum
Calandria Tube	Zircaloy	Aluminum	Aluminum

2.2. Experimental Results

In ZED-2, the change in critical D₂O level serves as an indirect measure of flooding reactivity. The validation process only requires the physical specifications for each critical configuration (e.g., D₂O height, number of flooded channels) such that the system can be modelled by a neutron transport code. The deviation from unity (or the measured value) of the calculated k_{eff} value is the computational bias. The NU benchmark described in [6] is simplified and therefore the experimental values (k_{eff}) are not exactly equal to 1. In this work MCNP 6.2 was used to determine the calculated k_{eff} values for the critical configurations [3].

For CVR validation, the important experimental result is the flooding bias, which is the difference in k_{eff} bias between the air-cooled and flooded configurations. A summary of experimental results is provided in Table II.

Table II. NU and MOX flooding experimental results.

	Height Difference (cm)	Air-Cooled Bias (pcm)	Flooded Bias (pcm)	Flooding Bias (pcm)
NU Experiment	18.07	-403	-472	-69
MOX Experiment	6.75	-168	-182	-14

Notably, a negative flooding bias was observed for both experiments. Experimental uncertainties and case-to-case correlations were approximated for both the NU and MOX systems based on the sensitivity analysis performed in reference [6]. The resultant estimated experimental reactivity uncertainties were 26 pcm and 13 pcm for the NU and MOX experiments, respectively. The MOX flooding experimental uncertainty was assumed to be smaller as fewer channels were flooded (55 versus 8), resulting in a smaller critical height difference. A comprehensive analysis of the MOX experiment would be required to accurately determine its experimental uncertainties.

3. VALIDATION RESULTS

3.1. Similarity

To relate a flooding bias measured in ZED-2 to the CVR bias of an application, the similarity of the two systems needs to be determined. Within the nuclear-data framework this can be achieved by the use of sensitivity coefficients, as given in Equation 2. Figure 3 compares reactivity sensitivity profiles S_ρ for some important cross sections.

Figure 3. CVR and draining (opposite of flooding) reactivity sensitivities of the application and experimental systems.

In Figure 3 it can be seen that the ^{238}U capture and ^{239}Pu fission sensitivities in the thermal range vary significantly between the experiments and the application. This is due to the temperature difference of the fuel and coolant, as listed in Table I. The major contributors to each system's nuclear data uncertainty are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 demonstrates that zirconium radiative capture, deuterium scatter and deuterium (n, 2n) reactions are the most significant sources of CVR uncertainty in the application.

The c index, also known as 'representivity', is often used to quantify how similar two systems are:

$$c = \frac{\mathbf{S}_a \mathbf{C} \mathbf{S}_e^T}{\sqrt{\mathbf{S}_a \mathbf{C} \mathbf{S}_a^T} \sqrt{\mathbf{S}_e \mathbf{C} \mathbf{S}_e^T}} \quad (5)$$

Where \mathbf{S}_e and \mathbf{S}_a are the sensitivity coefficients for the experimental and application systems and \mathbf{C} is the nuclear data covariance matrix. The c index can be used for k_{eff} (c_k) and reactivity ρ (c_ρ) responses. These quantities are summarized in Table III for the two ZED-2 experiments as compared to the CANDU application.

Table III. Similarity indices for the NU and MOX experiments

	ZED-2 NU	ZED-2 MOX
c_k	0.89	0.92
c_ρ	0.77	0.72

Figure 4. Nuclear data uncertainty contributions to CVR and flooding reactivity sensitivities of the application and experimental systems.

3.2. Nuclear Data Adjustments

TSURFER was used to perform the nuclear data adjustments and determine the associated CVR computational biases based on the ZED-2 experimental data. Adjustments were carried out using each experiment independently as well as in combination. The nuclear data adjustment results are presented in Table IV.

Table IV. Experimental adjustment results for CANDU CVR validation.

	ZED-2 NU	ZED-2 MOX	Combined
CVR Bias (pcm)	37.0	14.2	33.3
Adjusted Uncertainty	30.1	31.0	27.8
Uncertainty Reduction (%)	21.9	19.5	27.7

The adjustment results in Table IV are presented graphically in Figure 5. Notably, the adjustment results demonstrate a positive CVR bias for the application. However, the inclusion of the MOX data results in only a modest improvement compared to using the NU data alone.

4. DISCUSSION

This work explored the validation of CVR predictions using ZED-2 experiments in which NU and MOX fuel bundles were flooded. It was postulated that the inclusion of MOX flooding data to the existing NU experimental data would improve the validation case for an equilibrium plutonium-containing CANDU lattice. It was found that the MOX data were consistent with the existing NU data and reduced the application uncertainty by an additional 6 %. This improvement was limited in part because CVR uncertainty is dominated by deuterium scattering and (n, 2n) cross section uncertainties rather than by the cross sections of the fuel. Consequently, both the NU and MOX experiments provide redundant adjustments for these cross sections. The experimental uncertainties used for the MOX data were

Figure 5. Application CVR prior (original) and posterior (adjusted) distributions calculated using TSURFER and different sets of experimental data.

approximated based on previous analyses of ZED-2 experiments. A reduction of these uncertainties would significantly increase the value of the data from the MOX flooding experiment.

It is interesting to consider alternate experimental configurations that could be used to validate CVR bias predictions. There are a number of differences between the application and experimental systems presented in this work, such as the coolant temperature and tube compositions, that reduced the value of the measurements for CVR validation. Experiments utilizing different materials, and at elevated temperatures, have been carried out at ZED-2 in the past [9], and their inclusion could further improve the validation case.

This work considers the validation of a neutron transport code, and a corresponding nuclear data library, for a CANDU reactor application and demonstrates the potential value of ZED-2 flooding experiments within a validation framework. However, the actual implementation of these results for power reactor applications will require additional analyses, and may not involve the direct utilization of the calculated biases, or the adjusted nuclear data.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work describes the application of the TSUNAMI/TSURFER framework to two ZED-2 flooding experiments for validating CANDU CVR predictions: a natural uranium (NU) experiment already described in the IRPhE database, and a new mixed-oxide (MOX) flooding experiment. The additional MOX data was consistent with existing NU data; with both data sets independently suggesting that there is a positive CVR bias associated with the ENDF B-VII.1 nuclear data library. The CVR bias based on both experiments was determined to be 33 pcm (0.33 mk) with a 27.7 % reduction in nuclear data uncertainty, a further 6% reduction beyond the NU data alone. This work is a valuable example of how multiple critical benchmark experimental datasets can be used and compared within a reactivity validation framework.

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